

**Data Management Plan
for the submission of FOREFRONT (KKP_22) proposals**

Title and identification number of the proposal	Data_management_course_Sham_Jdeed
Principal investigator / Host institution	Sham Jdeed/ University of Debrecen
Scheduled starting date and conclusion of the project	01.09.2022-30.12.2022
Are research data being produced during the course of the project?	Yes
Who is responsible for the management of research data? (Contact details, if not a member of the project team)	All team members are responsible for data management, everyone is responsible for their own experiments. The PI is mainly responsible for research data management overall.
Please describe the type/nature of the data being produced during the course of the project.	Numerical data: RT-qPCR Images: Microscopy results, fluorescent images, western blotting images Sequencing data: RNA-Seq, ChIP-Seq ARID1A knock out vs wild type animals Galaxy software will be used for sequencing data analysis Cell profiler will be used for images analysis GraphPad prism software will be used for Numerical data analysis
Please describe the procedure of the data collection.	Mice will be exposed to skin damage through physical tools, and the healing time will be measured in wild type and ARID1AKO mice models. Blood and tissue samples from the injured area will be collected and used for RNA sequencing and RT-qPCR. The wounded area will be treated with healing ointments and the healing duration time will be measured.
Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored during the course of the project.	The generated data will be saved in the PC, hard device, Personal laptop, as well as in a shared

Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.	data management system such as Microsoft teams to be available for the whole team.
Please describe the accessibility of the research data.	After the course of the project sequencing data will be stored in Zenodo data repository And fluorescent images in IDR repository
Which research data of the project will be of open access? Is there any reason or necessity to restrict the accessibility of the research data?	All research members have accession to the research data The sequencing data No, among the research member, data should be accessible. Publically, only raw sequencing data and raw data that have been published
Do you use any standard metadata? (DublinCore, Datacite, etc.)	DublinCore standard metadata
Please describe where and how the metadata will be stored during the course of the project.	Metadata will be stored along within the rawdata in Zenodo or IDR repositories
Please describe how the metadata will be accessible?	Metadata will be accessible through the data repositories
Do you use standard or unique identifiers? (DOI, ORCID)	ORCID: 0000-0002-5098-3215
Please describe where and how the metadata, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.	Metadata will be stored along within the rawdata in Zenodo or IDR repositories
Does the handling of research data comply with the GDPR regulations?	Yes